

Historical Letters – Objectives, Design, Details

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1 Purpose

A letter-sending model with historically informed initial positions to reconstruct communication and archiving processes in the Republic of Letters, the 15th- to 17th-century form of scholarship [1].

The model is aimed at historians, willing to formalize historical assumptions about the letter-sending process itself and allows in principle to set heterogeneous social roles, e.g. to evaluate the role of gender or social status in the formation of letter exchange networks. The model furthermore includes a pruning process to simulate the loss of letters to critically assess the role of archiving biases e.g. in relation to gender, geographical regions, or power structures, in the creation of collections of letters (referred from here on as empirical letter archives).

Figure 1: An interface with visualizations allows changing main parameters and observing the resulting behaviour, see Sec. 6 for an explanation.

Each agent has an initial random topic vector, expressed as a RGB value. Topics are hypothetical, rather than representing some specific actual interests. The initial positions of the agents are based on a weighted random draw based on data from [2].

In each step, agents generate two neighbourhoods: one for sending letters and another one for potential targets to move towards. The probability to send letters is a self-reinforcing process. After each sending the internal topic of the receiver is updated as a movement in abstract space by a random amount towards the letters topic.

All send letters are tracked in a ledger which is the basis for further research on archival processes by performing random or targeted deletion of records. Changes in network measures are compared to results from empirical letter networks to find likely biases underlying the archive creation. The deletion can be selected as part of the agent-based simulation. In this case a range of network measures is calculated on copies of the ledger where letters have been deleted by different deletion strategies.

The model description follows the ODD (Overview, Design concepts, Details) protocol for describing individual- and agent-based models [9], as updated in [8].

2 Entities, state variables, and scales

The model has two different agents, the letter *senders/receivers* (SenderAgent) and the geographical *regions* (RegionAgent). Additional entities with state variables are the *HistoricalLetters* model itself and the *Nuts2Eu* space description. The regions correspond to the administrative European Unions NUTS2 levels, see [3], and cover the European Unions territory¹. Senders are placed in these regions, where several senders can be

¹This part of the code is based on the *Mesa Geo* example, see [4].

in the same region. Additionally, senders are connected to other senders by a social network. This social network can be pre-populated as an initial condition and then be grown by communication processes or it can be grown by the same processes with no initial connections.

The scales of the model are spatially the territory of the European Union, which is covered by the 242 regions with their corresponding geometric shape files, and population-wise the number of senders (e.g. between 10 and 1000 agents). The time scale evolves with discrete steps in the simulation, but is not empirically grounded. In other words, the steps do not reflect time intervals such as days, weeks, months or years.

2.1 SenderAgents

Senders are heterogeneous and defined by a matrix of parameters and variables, see Tab. 2.1 and 2.2 for definitions and domains. Senders in *HistoricalLetters* make two kinds of decisions in each step. They first try to send a letter to a suitable receiver and then try to move, see Sec. 8 for details. Both processes involve random decisions, see Sec. 4, and two distinct *neighbourhoods* (as outlined in the Purpose section), defined as circles in geographical space centered at the senders position. The circle with *letterRange* radius allows the senders to find potential receivers, which are not yet in their social network. The circle with *moveRange* radius gives the senders potential targets for changing their current geographical position. Senders are connected in a social network. Depending on the initial conditions of the HistoricalLetters model, the social network is an initial condition with short and long ranging connections, that then grows by the sending of letters, or the social network emerges by the ongoing letter sending. The social network itself is a property of the main model *HistoricalLetters*, see below.

Parameter	Domain	Description
unique.id	string	Unique identifier of the agent
activationWeight	{0,1}	Likelihood of getting activated in each round
similarityThreshold	{0,1}	Threshold for similarity between sender and receiver topic necessary for successful letter sending
moveRange	{0,1}	Range for finding neighbours for movement process ²
letterRange	{0,1}	Range for finding neighbours for letter sending

Table 2.1: Parameters for SenderAgents

²This as well as the letterRange are defined as percentage of average distance (0 → 0%, 1 → 100%) of all agents after random initialization.

The parameters are set during model initialization in the main model *HistoricalLetters*. While the majority of parameters are the same for all agents, the unique.id is always heterogeneous and activationWeight can be heterogeneous. Setting distributed, randomly drawn activationWeights, see Sec. 4, leads to agents with different likelihood of

getting activated in each round. The heuristic is that agents can have different likeliness of sending a letter in each round. During the scheduled runtime of the model, agents can change their internal topicVec, topicLedger and the counter variables by receiving or sending a letter, see Sec. 8. The topicVec describes the currently held abstract topic of the sender. The sender’s topicLedger is a list of all previously held topics. Whenever an agent receives a letter from another agent, there is a chance for an updating of the internal topicVec state. What exactly determines if the topicVec space is updated is explained in the following sections.

Variable	Domain	Description
topicVec	$\{0,1\}^3$	Current 3D topic position, modelled as r,g,b values
topicLedger	topicVec^k	List of previously held topicVec vectors, with k the number of successful letters sending events
geometry	$\{\text{float}, \text{float}\}$	Current position of agent as latitude and longitude coordinates in EPSG:3857 projection
numLettersReceived	\mathbb{N}	Number of received letters
numLettersSend	\mathbb{N}	Number of send letters

Table 2.2: Variables of SenderAgents

2.2 RegionAgents

The RegionAgents, *regions* in short, are introduced for visualization purposes and have parameters and variables described in Table 2.3. The *regions* represent geographical sections of the administrative European Union’s NUTS2 levels, version 2021, see [3] for a description. During the model run each region maintains a dictionary of currently contained agents and their topicVec vectors as well as a scaling number (the number of the senders already received letters). This is used to calculate a current weighted average main topic of the region, which determines its coloring in a visualization. If no agents are in the region the color defaults to gray.

2.3 HistoricalLetters entity

The model parameters, space, and scheduler are organized in the main model, *HistoricalLetters*. This model has a number of variables and parameters. One set of parameters is chosen at each model initialization and directly determines the behaviour of agents, see Table 2.1 for an explanation of the parameters:

- moveRange
- letterRange

Name	Domain	Description
unique_id	string	Unique ID of the region, given by the NUTS2 region identifier.
geometry	$(\{\text{float}, \text{float}\})^n$	Shape of the NUTS2 region, given as polygon in geojson format, i.e. list of coordinates in EPSG:3857 projection
senders_in_region	$(\text{unique.id}:\{\text{topicVec}, \text{scale}\})^j$	Dictionary of senders and their current topic vector and scale (the number of already received letters) in region
has_main_topic	$\{0,1\}^3$	Weighted average of all current topics of senders in this region, modelled as r,g,b values. Defaults to (0.5,0.5,0.5) (gray) if no sender in region.

Table 2.3: Parameters and variables of RegionAgents

- similarityThreshold

Another set of parameters is set at initialization to change the model behaviour, see Table 2.4. The number of senders is set with the population parameter. Other parameters determine if senders should have heterogeneous activation probabilities or if a pruning routine should run at the end of a model run. The social network of SenderAgents in the model can already be pre-populated initially, see Sec 5.

Name	Domain	Description
population	\mathbb{N}	The number of agents for a simulation run
useActivation	bool	Whether to use heterogeneous activation probabilities for the agents
runPruning	bool	Whether to run a pruning step after the model run or return the full letter ledger
useSocialNetwork	bool	Whether to pre-populate a social network at model initialization
longRangeNetworkFactor	$\{0,1\}$	Social edge creation at initialization: Weight of random draw from long range neighbours
shortRangeNetworkFactor	$\{0,1\}$	Weight of random draw from short range neighbours

Table 2.4: Model parameters of HistoricalLetters

The model makes use of two input files, which are set by the input parameters in Tab. 2.5. RegionData is used to create the RegionAgents, see above, and has the form of

a GeoJSON file with the NUTS2 regions as features. To start the model with historically meaningful initial geographical placement of the agents, the `populationDistributionData` reads in a CSV file with population estimates for medieval cities [2], see Sec. 5.

Name	Filetype	Description
<code>regionData</code>	GeoJSON	GeoJSON shapefiles for EU NUTS2 regions, version 2021, see [3].
<code>populationDistributionData</code>	CSV	Estimates for population and area relationships of medieval european cities, see [2].

Table 2.5: Input parameters of `HistoricalLetters`

Name	Domain	Description
Output variables		
<code>socialNetwork</code>	<code>networkx MultiDiGraph</code>	The directed network between sender and receivers with potentially multiple edges.
<code>letterLedger</code>	<code>list</code>	A list of all send letters with sender and receiver IDs and their location IDs during sending. In addition the time step of sending and the send topic are noted.
<code>movements</code>	\mathbb{N}	The number of successful movements of agents.
Internal variables		
<code>scaleSendInput</code>	$(\text{unique_id: numLettersReceived})^j$	Dictionary of sender id and number of their received letters.
<code>updatedTopicsDict</code>	$(\text{unique_id: topicVec})^j$	Dictionary of sender id and topic vector

Table 2.6: Variables of `HistoricalLetters`

Beyond the model’s parameters, three main output variables are tracked, see Table 2.6. The social network of senders and receivers is dynamically growing by the letter exchanges and tracked as *socialNetwork*. The *letterLedger* contains information about all successful letter-sending events. The variable *movements* keeps track of successful movements of the senders, see below. At the end of a full run, the data is collected, see Sec. 3.

In addition to these output variables two other variables are necessary to separate the processes of the model run. During each round of one step of the model, senders are

activated in random order. Since the interaction of the agents depends, e.g., on the number of received letters, the updated information of which agent received which number of letters and changed their topic vector to which new value, has to be noted but not applied in the same round. For this purpose *scaleSendInput* and *updatedTopicsDict* keep track of the changes in one round. The information is then used to update all agents before the next round of the model run.

2.4 Nuts2Eu entity

For the definition of the geographical space in which senders exchange letter and move, an example from the mesa-geo package is reused and slightly extended. See [4] for the example. The *Nuts2Eu* entity is a space with well defined spacial coordinates in EPSG:3857 projection. This allows to calculate meaningful distances between agents and introduce the different necessary ranges of the model. The entity has as only variable a dictionary of regionIDs mapping to the RegionAgents. All processes of movement of senders from one region to the other are delegated to the level of the regions, see Sec. 8.

2.5 Scheduler

The model uses the scheduler for random activation implemented in the mesa package. See [5] for an introductory tutorial discussing this scheduler. In the model, the schedule is necessary to activate the agents individual step functions, see Sec. 8.

2.6 Data collection functions

The model has four different data collection functions, which are called after the end of a simulation run, started by the models *run function*. These are *getPrunedLedger*, *getScaledLetters*, *getScaledMovements* and *getComponents*. The two functions *getScaledLetters* and *getScaledMovements* return the number of send letters and successful movements respectively divided by the number of steps. *GetComponents* returns the number of connected components of the social network. If an initial social network is used in the model run, this will most likely be equal to one component throughout the simulation run, since the social network forms a connected network already from initialization. *GetPrunedLedger* has two possible return datasets. If *runPruning* is false, it returns the full letter ledger containing all information. If *runPruning* is true, it runs the pruning routine on the full data and then only returns information about the statistics of the full and reduced datasets, see Sec. 8.

3 Process overview and scheduling

3.1 Simulation setup

At initialization of the main model HistoricalLetters with the required (Table 2.4) and optional (Table 2.5) parameters, a number of initialization steps are run, see Sec. 5 for details. These are ordered as follows:

- Initialize the RegionAgents
- Add RegionAgents to space
- Initialize the SenderAgents
- Add SenderAgents to regions
- Add senders to scheduler
- If useSocialNetwork is true, setup initial social network for senders
- Setup model reporter functions

3.2 Simulation step

Once the model is initialized, it can be run for a number of time steps with the *run function*. In each time step senders are updated sequentially and at random. A time-step is defined as the length of time it takes to update all agents. For each time step of the model, the *step function* is called. This call first updates the model variable scaleSendInput and then activates a step of the scheduler. The scheduler then randomly activates senders. Note that datacollection is only performed at the end of the run function, not in each step. This is to increase performance but also limits the possible type of output data, i.e. no intermediate data collection is possible in this implementation.

As an example consider a model run of 10 steps. The following steps are then run in the given order.

- 0 Repeat 10 times:
 - 1 Update scaleSendInput model variable
 - 2 Scheduler calls agents step function
 - 2.1 Agent performs sender step
 - 2.2 Agent performs move step
 - 3 Go to 1
- 4 Collect data

3.2.1 Sender step

Each sender agent performs a sequence of sub-stepping:

- Read new topicVec and append to the personal topic ledger if different from the old one
- Random draw from $[0, 1]$ if agent gets activated or not
- if activated, find neighbours for 1) moving and 2) sending letters to
- Send letter
- Move

For details of the processes refer to Sec. 8.

4 Design concepts

Emergence Starting from random initial topics and positions, in the course of the simulation the SenderAgents form clusters both in geographical as well as the abstract topic space. Each communication event connects agents in a social network, leading to emergent, self-reinforcing social structures. Together with the self-reinforcement of the likely receivers, this leads to some sender agents emerging as the hubs of this sender-receiver network.

Adaption SenderAgents adapt to their neighbours in their currently held topic with a rate set in the model. Since the likeliness of moving is a 90/10 random process, adaption on geographical space is happening at a slower pace.

Objectives SenderAgents try to find suitable letter receivers and thereby increase the number of successful letter sending steps.

Sensing SenderAgents have a range for sensing suitable letter receivers in their geographical vicinity. They also make use of their emergent social network to find communication partners. They furthermore sense the receivers and their own previously held topics, to select a potential topic of the letter to be sent.

Interaction The letter-sending process forms the interaction between SenderAgents. After having simulated one step, the internal states of both sender and receiver are updated. Only the receivers' internal topic state is changed. The sender continues to hold the current topic. See Sec. 8 for details of this process.

Stochasticity Stochastic processes are used at the model initialization to have random initial placements of senders. Sending and moving also use stochastic processes such that not every agent in every round sends a letter or moves. See Sec. 8 for details.

Observation The output of the model is the Letter Ledger. While the ledger is populated during modeling steps, data is collected only at the end of the simulation run. Due to memory limitations, the internal trajectories of topics for individual agents are not collected by default. Similarly, the trajectories of population dynamics of RegionAgents, and the average topic in these, is not collected.

To reduce the memory requirements of ledger data, the simulation can instead be run with automated pruning at the end of a simulation run.

5 Initialisation

The initialization process is started from the main model HistoricalLetters. Parameters influencing the initialization of agents are taken from this main model.

5.1 Initialize regions

For the initialization of the region agents, a GEOJSON file with the definition of the EUs NUTS2 regions is read in by the main model. This file contains the shape of each region as a polygon of coordinates in EPSG:3857 projection. For each region the mesa-geo agent creator creates a new agent with the NUTS ID as the unique id. Initially the region agent has an empty dictionary for the senders in that region and the default main topic of (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), which denotes grey colour in RGB. Each region agent is then added to the model space.

5.2 Initialize senders

During initialization, two random processes are applied. The position $[x, y](t = 0)$ of each agent is randomly drawn from a weighted distribution reflecting medieval population projections, see [2]. Higher populated areas are more likely to be drawn as initial positions. Furthermore, each agent is started with a random topic $a_k(t = 0) = (a_r, a_g, a_b)$ consisting of three individually and unweighted randomly drawn numbers between zero and one. This corresponds to a value for a color code in RGB format. Every model run therefore starts with randomly drawn initial coordinates for the senders.

If at initialization of the model the option useActivation is set to True, each agent is initialized with a unique activationWeight w_i , randomly drawn between zero and one.

The `activationWeight` is then used during the simulation run. At each step and for each agent, a number is drawn from a list of zero (agent is not activated) and one (agent is activated). The `activationWeight` w_i sets the in-balance $1 - w_i$ to draw a zero, i.e. a high `activationWeight` lowers the chance to not getting activated.

The agents values for `moveRange`, `letterRange`, and `similarityThreshold` are set by the main model.

5.3 Initialize social network

If the option `useSocialNetwork` is set to `True`, a social network of the agents is created at initialization. In this case, the parameters for short and long range network factors determine the likeliness of drawing a target from lists of short and long range neighbours of a source agent. Short range neighbours are defined as those agents within a geographic distance set by the `moveRange` parameter times the mean distances between all agents. Long range neighbours are all agents not in the short range neighbours list. Changing the `moveRange` parameter therefore has a strong influence on the initial social network.

Depending on the chosen parameters for the likeliness of short or long ranging social connections, the social network can have small world character or not. A `shortRangeNetworkFactor` of 0.4 and a `longRangeNetworkFactor` of 0.3 have been tested to result in an initial social network with small word character. These parameteres are set as default during model initialization.

If a target in either the short or long range neighbourhood is drawn, the directed social edge is created in the direction from target to source.

To keep track of the creation of social edges during a simulation run, edges created at initialization have the attribute of `step=0`.

6 Visualization

The current implementation of the `HistoricalLetters` ABM includes a visualization interface, see Fig. 1. This interface displays a map with the current position and `topicVec` of all agents, three graphs showing the number of movements, clusters and letters sent divided by step number and controls for the population size, `similarityThreshold`, `moveRange`, `letterRange`, `useActivation` and `useSocialNetwork`.

Region agents take the color of the current main topic and cover the geographic extend of the respective NUTS2 region. Sender agents are visualized as circles with a fixed radius and the color corresponding to their current `topicVec`.

The interface allows to run, pause and reset the model, change parameters and increase the speed. Using the interface simple assumptions of the model can be confirmed, e.g.

if limiting the `moveRange` leads to a more stationary simulation, and a high `similarityThreshold` leads to more changes in the agents topics.

7 Input data

Two datasets are used for input. One is the estimated population density, cited above. The other are the shapefiles of the EU NUTS2 regions. Thus, space is defined by modern administrative boundaries. This is meant only to give a geographically meaningful tiling of the EU region. No state boundaries, early modern or present-day, impact on the senders' movements. The datasets are provided with the software code, and additionally uploaded to CoMSES.

8 Submodels

8.1 Activating a sender agent

In each round, at activation the sender first reads in the new `topicVec` from the model variable `updatedTopicsDict` and appends it to the personal topic ledger if the new topic is different from the current topic. It then performs a random choice between zero and one, weighted either with one (i.e. the agent is always activated) or the `heterogeneousActivationWeight`. If it draws a one, the sender becomes active and the sub-steps continue. Drawing a zero means the agent will not send letters or move in this step.

8.2 Find neighbours

If the sender is activated, two neighbourhoods are created for that agent. Based on the set values for `moveRange` and `letterRange`, the model's space is used to create circles around the sender's position. All other senders in these circles are considered neighbours for this step. `moveRange` is used to find neighbours for the move step and `letterRange` is used to find neighbours for the letter sending step. Senders then perform first a letter sending step and then a move step.

8.3 Sending a letter

In the letter sending step, the sender receives a list of all current neighbours' ids as strings. This is extended by the sender's social network neighbours' ids. In the social network other agents are considered neighbours, if a directed edge exists from the sender to the other agent. To make the letter sending a *self-reinforcing process*, a distribution

is created taking both social and geographical neighbours. Each id string is added N times, where N is the number of letters this other agent with the given id has already received. A sender with, e.g., 10 received letters will then have its id 10 times in the selection. From this distribution of ids, one id is randomly picked. This corresponds to a Polya urn model³.

If a potential receiver has been picked (the list could be empty), the sender carries on to select a topic of the letter to write. The sender randomly chooses from a joined list of its own and the receiver's previous topics. With this random choice of a letter topic, the distance between the chosen topic and the current topic vector of the receiver is calculated. If it falls below the predefined *similarityThreshold*, the letter sending process continues. The counters of the receiver for numLettersReceived and of the sender for numLettersSend are increased and the information is appended to the corresponding nodes of the social network. In the model's social network, an additional edge is created from the sender to the receiver, with the step time as an attribute of the edge. For the receiver of the letter, an updated personal topicVec is calculated as a random movement in 3D along the line between the receivers current topicVec and the topic chosen for the letter. The new topic is updated in the main models updatedTopicsDict variable. Finally, the information of the letter sending process is appended to the models letterLedger. This includes the senders' and receivers' ids and locations, the topic of the letter and the time of sending. This concludes the sending step.

8.4 Moving

Senders can additionally change their geographical position. For this process, the geographical neighbourhood is used to find suitable positions of neighbouring agents. The process of moving contains three additional random processes. If a sender has potential neighbour targets, the decision to move is a random weighted draw from zero (do not move) or one (move). The weights are 0.9 for zero, and 0.1 for one. If the agent selects to move, a target position is randomly selected from a list of all neighbour positions weighted by the corresponding number of received letters of the neighbour. Those who receive more letters are thus more likely to attract agents to move towards them. A geographical line between the senders current position and the selected neighbours position is created. The sender moves a random portion along this line towards the selected target. The new current region id is calculated and the senders new position is updated in the Nuts2EU space. For some special cases, the new position might have no overlap with a geographic region, e.g., when the new position would correspond to a place in the channel of England. In this case the movement process is aborted and the sender stays at the old position. Only for cases of successful movements the main models counter on movements is increased.

³See e.g. wikipedia for more information: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plya_urn_model

8.5 Pruning of letter data

To simulate the effect of archival practices on the resulting network structure, the implementation of the ABM includes a routine for deletion of the letter ledger data. If the model parameter *usePruning* is true, the datacollector function of the model runs the deletion routine on the letter ledger. At the end of this routine, only statistics of several deletion procedures are returned, not the ledger data itself.

At the end of a simulation run, the letter ledger contains all successful letter sending events. This data is used to create a baseline network between senders and receivers weighted with the number of send letters. Each node additionally contains the information of the last region ID of the agent, i.e. the agents region at the end of the simulation run. Each edge between two agents has an additional attribute that takes note of the steps in which a letter was send between the two parties.

What influences survival of letters? On this baseline network three main assumptions about the likeliness for the survival of archival material are made: survival depends on the reputation of the sender/receiver as measured by communication events, survival depends on the number of agents in a region, or survival depends on the age of the communication event, where older letters are more likely to be lost.

For the assumption of reputation the baseline network is sorted by the node degree in descending order. For the regional assumption the network is sorted by the number of senders that have the same last region id, i.e. regions containing more agents are at the top. Regions that contain no agent at the end of the simulation have a number of zero occupancy. For the assumption on the age of the letter sending event, the network is sorted in descending order by the time step, i.e. last step to first step. To be able to compare the effect of this sorting routines, for each approach a random reshuffle is created as a null hypothesis.

Testing the effect of the assumptions On each of these thus sorted networks two main classes of random distributions are appended. The first class consists of the uniform, exponential and beta random distribution, the second class consists of the log normal random distribution with three different parameter set.⁴

The random distributions are merged with the original letter ledger by setting for each communication event the corresponding random distribution value for sender, receiver, sender location and receiver location and then calculate the weighted product of the two probabilities. This process reflects the assumption that the survivability of a letter both depends on who received the letter but also who send the letter. Similarly, the survivability of a letter can depend on the region it was sent to but also from where it

⁴For more information on random number generation, see e.g. <https://numpy.org/doc/stable/reference/random/generator.html>.

was sent. In the case of the survivability due to age, a mapping from the created random distributions to the ledger is directly possible, since each ledger entry has only one time argument, i.e. the simulation step in which the letter was send.

Each combination of the survival hypothesis together with the applied random distribution corresponds to a historical argument about the likelihood of archival material to survive.

Sampling the letter data For each of the chosen distributions a random sampling of the letter data is performed with the weight of the sampling process given by the distribution data. The different chosen distributions reflect different assumption of the processes of deletion. The amount of data sampled ranges from 90% to only 10% of the data. This corresponds to different levels of conservation of the letter data.

For each sampled dataset a reduced network is created by the above introduced routine and the resulting statistics are calculated using the Python package `igraph`. Statistics include the number of components, the average path length, the diameter, the modularity, the transitivity, the cohesion, the assortativity, the indegree distribution, the average indegree, the centrality and an estimate for a power law fit.

Together with the model parameters, the type of distribution, the amount of deletion and the iteration number, the resulting statistics is added to the output dataset. Each iteration of the pruning thus gives a range of network fingerprints. These steps of pruning can then be calculated several times. Due to the randomness of the processes, it is unlikely that any two iterations will yield the same results.

To test hypothesis on the processes of archiving, the resulting network statistics are compared to the original full network statistics, and suitable empirical letter meta data, e.g. from the Letter Sampo project [6] or CorrespSearch [7]. A combination of parameters that yields statistics more similar to empirical data is argued to be a more likely candidate for the historical process of archiving.

8.6 An example model setup: batch run

The above introduced pruning routines need to be run for a range of different parameters of the main model. This allows to check for dependencies of effects on e.g. population sizes, or the role of initial conditions. The settings are chosen for a simpler interpretability of the results. To this aim, the similarity threshold is set to 1 such that each found receiver is written to. Several iterations of this basic scenario are run, with a set of chosen parameters each. The `moveRange` parameter is kept fixed at 0.05, i.e. there is no long-ranging movement and the process is dominated by letter sending. Each combination of the following parameters is run 10 times each.

- Population = [100, 200, 300]

- Letter range = [0.25, 0.5, 0.75]
- Small world = [True, False]
- Activation = [True, False]
- Steps = [100, 200]

The resulting letter ledgers are used to simulate the different deletion processes.

9 Sources

Software documentation: <https://scientificcommunication.readthedocs.io>

Source code: <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/modelsen/sciencecommunicationmodels>

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